

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF COCOON CULTIVATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article describes the state of cocoon cultivation in Uzbekistan and the ongoing work on its increase. Ways to reproduce the cocoon are described.

Keywords: Cocoon worm, mulberry tree, cocoon production, cocoon clusters.

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КОКОНОВЕДЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. В статье описывается состояние коконоводства в Узбекистане и проводимая работа по его увеличению. Описаны способы размножения кокона.

Ключевые слова: коконный червь, тутовое дерево, коконообразование, коконные грозди.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, cocoon worms have been reared and silk obtained since ancient times. Various clothes and carpets are made from silk. Products made of silk, natural, soft, elegant, bright color, ripe and durable, are very popular. Margilan atlases, adras and bekasams were famous everywhere. Fabrics and clothes made of silk were sent from Uzbekistan to the northern countries (now the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan). The name "Great Silk Road" did not appear by itself.

In the early years of Uzbekistan's independence, attention to cocooning was somewhat reduced. The cocoon breeders mainly fed them from their homes and raised the cocoons. They were given only a sack of flour and 10 kg of cottonseed oil when the cocoon seeds were distributed without proper remuneration for their labor. Tutzors were used for raising livestock.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Decision of the President of the country No. PQ-2856 of March 29, 2017 on measures to organize the activities of the "Uzbekipaksanoat" association" was of great importance in the development of cocooning. Based on this decision, the "Uzbekipaksanoat" association was established, and "Agropilla" enterprises were merged into the association. Foreign experience, especially the world leaders in cocoon production, established contacts with countries such as China, India, South Korea, and Thailand on cocoon production. In 2017-2019, soft-leaved mulberry seedlings were brought from China and mulberry groves were established. High-yielding and resistant bollworm seeds were brought. As a result, cocoon production increased year by year.

Indicators of cocoon preparation in Uzbekistan.

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Cocoon, thousand t	12.5	17.9	21.4	20.9	24.4

As can be seen from the table data, since 2017, cocoon production in our country has increased rapidly. In 2020, 24,400 tons of cocoons were produced in our country, which is twice as much as in 2017.

The production of cocoons in our country will continue to increase at a high rate. Because a solid base is being created for this. Serkhosil, soft-leaved tussocks have been established and

placed at the disposal of "Uzbekipaksanoat" enterprises, cocoons that meet modern requirements are being built, and enterprises specializing in the production of silkworm seeds are being equipped and modernized with new equipment and technology. Citizens who have grown cocoons are exempted from income tax, and their periods of one season of work are transferred to one year of work experience for pension purposes.

RESULTS

The clusters that are being formed play an important role in increasing the production of cocoons. The clusters cover the entire process from cocoon care, cocoon feeding and cocooning, silk spinning, to the production of finished silk products. In 2017, silkworms were reared once, in some regions twice (season), now they are reared mainly for three seasons, in Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions up to four seasons (up to 4 times). Only during the years 2019-2021, the volume of silkworms grown increased from 158,000 to 240,000 boxes, i.e. 1.5 times, and the area of silkworms increased to 54,800 hectares. Not only elegant fabrics, but more than 6 types of products are obtained from cocoons. Especially mushroom is considered an important raw material of the pharmaceutical industry.

DISCUSSION

Currently, 76 cocooning clusters have been established. The number of joint ventures processing cocoons is increasing. As a result, elegant, brightly colored, soft clothes, pillows, blankets, and beautiful carpets are made from silk fabrics. Finished products made of coir are popular not only in the domestic market, but also in European countries, and the export volume is increasing year by year. The fact that the natural conditions of our country are suitable for raising cocoon worms, the increase of soft-leaved trees, and most importantly, the organization of clusters with modern specialists covering all processes of cocoon preparation, show that cocoon cultivation in our country is promising.

CONCLUSIONS

The Republic of Uzbekistan is the 5th largest producer of silk kurti cocoon after China, Japan, India and Brazil. About 30,000 people work in network enterprises. In the country in 2020, 18.9 thousand tons of cocoons, i. s. 1,200.3 tons of silk thread, 95 tons of silk carpets were produced in the enterprises, 5.336 mln. m² silk fabrics were produced. In foreign countries, USA, FRG, Japan, France, Great Britain, and Italy are in the leading position in the production of silk gauze, especially gauze from synthetic and artificial silk fibers. Japan, China, India, Jan. Extraction of silk from silkworm cocoons and silk fabrics in European countries and Brazil i. Ch. developed.

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